

A study on income inequalities in the special development plan, with special reference to Kalyana Karnataka region

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12798967>

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Abstract

Objectives: The present paper analyzes inter-district disparities in the Kalyana Karnataka Region, and there is major objective of the study is to analyse the income inequality between inter-district Kalyana Karnataka Region. To know the causes and policy implications of the inter-district disparities in the Kalyana Karnataka Region analysis of the study.

Methods: The study has been carried out based on secondary source data for the census years 2011–12 and 2021–22. For this study, district-level data has been collected from sources like the Statistical Handbook, the Karnataka Economic Survey 2011–12–2021–22, research papers, books, newspapers, reports, and websites. Some statistical tools are measures of central tendency, measures of dispersion, forecasting, minimum, maximum, sum, and percentage, ANOVA, and correlation calculation.

Findings/results: It has been found that the study found that disparity persists in inter-district levels of per capita income to identify the income inequality among inter-districts in the Kalyana Karnataka region and used data to compare between the 2013 and 2022 Census. Karnataka growth per capita income is increasing year by year.

Suggestions: The administration should raise the percentage of plan and non-expenditure on Kalyana Karnataka regional and also make all-inclusive plans for income growthiest, and also to allocate or generate new employment programs, it's helpful to remove the disparities.

Keywords: SDP, disparities, income, GDDP, investment

1. Introduction

Income disparities have occurred across the world. Even in developed countries, disparities are wide and the contexts of developed nations are having massive inequities in socioeconomic pointers. In the context of India, Karnataka is also a backward economy having so many difficulties in Kalyana Karnataka Region. To have rural-urban development in particular and development in general the need of the hour is to improve the different development indicators across the region equally. The disparities in different developmental indicators like education, health, agricultural productivity, employment, etc. across the Kalyana Karnataka Region of Karnataka lead to inter-district disparities in the state.

The spatial disparities in the Kalyana Karnataka Region in an economy like Karnataka are caused by several factors

ranging from infrastructure, availability of natural resources, industrialisation, urbanization, etc. along with different physiographical and geographical factors. The study of inter-district disparities in the Kalyana Karnataka Region of Karnataka which are caused by different factors is very important for policy implications regarding equitable development in the region and rural development in general. The existing study attempts to analyse the factors of understanding inequalities in the Kalyana Karnataka Region and their extent in the different districts of Karnataka. Here, the study investigates the various factors influencing disparities in the Kalyana Karnataka Region development of Karnataka based on secondary data sources from the time of 2011 to 2022 censuses which cover seven districts like Bidar, Gulbarga, Koppal, Raichur, Ballari, and Vijayanagara. Among the broad factors determining

variations in Kalyana Karnataka Region development mention may be various developmental infrastructural facilities, resource availability, government expenditure on a rural development program, and industrial and urban growth. Here, the rural infrastructure has been categorized into four indicators the number of primary educational institutions, the number of primary health centres, irrigation facilities, and rural roads. Like rural infrastructure resource availability factors include variables like the average size of operational holding and access to land in the rural area. Again, the study also wants to discover the significant factors that lead to disparities in the Kalyana Karnataka Region in particular and economic development in general.

2. Review of literature and conceptual background

1. Aabid Ahmad Koka, and Muddasir Ali Mir. (2018) ^[1]. The research indicates that the development of health facilities in Kashmir is not distributed equally. Merely 10% of the districts fall into the category of highly developed, 50% fall into the category of undeveloped, 20% fall into the category of backward, and 20% fall into the category of extremely backward.
2. R V Dadibhavi, S T Bagalkoti and Sahana Joshi. (2006) ^[3]. The findings unequivocally show that significant infrastructure investment is needed, particularly in the developing states. These states have few opportunities for private investment, hence governmental expenditure is required for most infrastructure development.
3. Laxmi Narayan (2011) ^[4], "Some Aspects of Inter District Disparities in Haryana" This research attempts to examine various aspects of the inter-district differences in Haryana. A variety of metrics, mostly categorized as economic, educational, and health indicators, are used to examine inter-district differences in Haryana.
4. Reena Rai (2014) ^[5] Based on the empirical data, the indicators that have impacted the degree of development include law and order, the percentage of non-farm income, and health development. In order to encourage NGOs, educators, and government agencies to create the right learning environment in schools and persuade first-generation students that doors are open for them, in addition to building educational infrastructure in underdeveloped districts, the government should implement special programs. To close the gap, officials should determine the causes of the growing imbalance at the broken-down level and take the necessary action.
5. Mallikarjun G. Naik and Dr. V. Sharada. *et al*, (2013) ^[6]. The methodologies used in this study are descriptive. There have been significant advancements in educational growth in a few state districts. Thus, measures are implemented to lessen the differences in educational growth throughout the state's districts, including expanding the number of schools, enhancing the facilities, hiring more teachers, etc.

6. Dr. Rajeshwari U R, Prof. Emmanuel P. J. (2015) ^[7]. According to a study, interventions meant to promote general health may unintentionally increase group disparities; indicators are a crucial instrument for evaluating the impact. However, lower levels of population development and inadequate infrastructure amenities continue to characterize the backward areas.

3. Need for the study

Inter-district in Kalyana Karnataka, income differences were common. It has attracted the attention of the government, policymakers, and parliamentarians over time, period and they have thought about it. Despite the government allocating a sizable sum of money, the government's in-state state wealth disparity has remained unabated come disparities have remained unabated. This article makes a significant effort to pinpoint income gaps in economic statistics, such as per-capita income, The aforementioned indicators still show instabilities even after structural reforms; as a result, this study aims to shed light on interregional disparities (specifically, those within the Kalyana Region of the state of Karnataka State) to call focus to the requirement for them to encourage equitable regional development in the nation.

4. Data methodology

The study has been carried out based on secondary source data for the census years 2011–12 and 2021–22. The existing study, based on objectives, is satisfied with the help of the district-level data of Kalyana Karnataka, which has been compiled from different secondary data sources. Census Report, Karnataka Economic Survey 2012–22, Research papers, books, newspapers, reports, etc. have used various statistical tools, including measures of central tendency, measures of dispersion, forecasting, minimum, maximum, sum, and percentage, ANOVA, and correlation calculations. These calculations have been performed with the help of secondary data sources.

5. Objectives of the study

The main objectives of the study are

1. To study the income inequality between inter-district Kalyana Karnataka Region.
2. To identify the causes and Policy Implication of the inter-district disparities in the Kalyana Karnataka Region.

6. Hypothesis of the study

1. **H₀**: There is no substantial deviation between per capital income between Kalyana Karnataka districts.
2. **H₁**: There is a substantial deviation between per capital income between Kalyana Karnataka districts.

7. The income inequality between inter-districts in Kalyana Karnataka region

Table 1: Per Capital Income Growth in Karnataka

Year	Per Capita Income (₹)	Year-on-Year Growth Rate (%)
2011-12	90,263	-
2012-13	1,02,319	13.4
2013-14	1,18,829	16.1
2014-15	1,30,024	9.4
2015-16	1,48,108	13.9
2016-17	1,69,898	14.7
2017-18	1,85,840	9.4
2018-19	2,04,804	10.2
2019-20 (S.R.E.)	2,22,002	8.4
2020-21 (F.R.E.)	2,36,451	6.5
2021-22 (A.E.)	2,78,786	17.9
Total	18,87,324	-
Average	1,71,575	-

Note: Note: S.R.E.: Second Revised Estimates, F.R.E.: First Revised Estimates, A.E.: Advance Estimates.

Source: Karnataka Economic Survey 2021-22

Here's an analysis of the per capita income data for Karnataka from 2011–12 to 2021–22. The per capita income of Karnataka has shown a consistent upward trend over the years. The per capita income increased from ₹90,263 in 2011-12 to ₹2,78,786 in 2021-22. The year-on-year growth rate is positive throughout the period, indicating steady

economic growth. The highest percentage increase occurred between 2011–12 and 2012–13, with a growth of about 13.4%. The second significant increase is observed from 2020–21 to 2021–22, with a growth of approximately 17.9%. The total per capita income over the 11 years is ₹1,887,324.

Table 2: Kalyana Karnataka Districts wise per capital Income at Current Prices (in Rs.)

Year	Ballari	Bidar	Kalaburagi	Koppal	Raichur	Yadgir
2013	108454	70543	67886	73916	73851	69014
2014	114138	70339	71085	75598	76498	69177
2015	116807	73892	65493	74134	78057	68928
2016	134150	85713	83619	82787	90530	81845
2017	150319	98754	92098	96036	95451	103677
2018	161715	100234	99322	100497	105654	97353
2019	124812	76528	70066	75278	80735	79854
Mean	130056.4286	82286.14286	78509.85714	82606.57143	85825.14286	81406.85714
Median	124812	76528	71085	75598	80735	79854
Standard Deviation	19801.96518	12840.77305	13245.24062	11184.72226	11723.23669	14211.00664
Sample Variance	392117825	164885452.5	175436399.1	125098012	137434278.5	201952709.8
Range	53261	29895	33829	26581	31803	34749
Minimum	108454	70339	65493	73916	73851	68928
Maximum	161715	100234	99322	100497	105654	103677
Sum	910395	576003	549569	578246	600776	569848

Sources: Karnataka Economic Survey 2021-22

Table No-2 Here's an analysis of the per capita income data for Ballari, Bidar, Kalaburagi, Koppal, Raichur, and Yadgir from 2013 to 2019. Shows a consistent increase in income from 2013 to 2018, peaking at ₹161,715 in 2018. There is a noticeable drop in 2019 to ₹124,812. Bidar district Income slightly fluctuates but generally increases, reaching its peak at ₹100,234 in 2018. Kalaburagi district Fluctuating income with a notable peak in 2018 at ₹99,322. Significant decline in 2019 to ₹70,066. Raichur district gradually increased from 2013 to 2018, peaking at ₹105,654 in 2018. Yadgir district General upward trend with significant variability, peaking at ₹103,677 in 2017. Drop to ₹79,854 in 2019.

Ballari has the highest average per capita income (130056.4286), indicating better economic performance compared to the other districts. Ballari also has the highest median income (₹124,812). Kalaburagi has the lowest median income (₹71,085). A higher standard deviation in Yadgir (₹14,211.01) indicates more variability in income; Koppal has the lowest standard deviation (₹11,184.72). Yadgir has the highest variance (₹201,952,709.8). The range shows the difference between the highest ₹53,261, and Koppal has the lowest range ₹26,581. The sum of income over the years shows a total economic output of 910,395.

Table 3: Forecasting of the Kalyana Karnataka Districts wise per capital Income at Current Prices (in Rs.)

Years	Ballari	Bidar	Kalaburagi	Koppal	Raichur	Yadgir
2020	148242	69115	90279	80660.39	79893.05	68995.56
2021	153926	68911	93478	81501.92	79946.99	68942.21
2022	159610	68707	96677	82344.54	80250.87	68975.54
2023	165294	68503	99876	83186.43	80388.18	68971.24
2024	170978	68299	103075	84028.51	80567.12	68971.31
2025	176662	68095	106274	84870.59	80746.06	68971.38
2030	205082	67075	122269	89080.96	81640.75	68971.73

Table No. 03 Here's an analysis of the per capita income data for Ballari, Bidar, Kalaburagi, Koppal, Raichur, and Yadgir from 2020 to 2030. Ballari district shows a consistent increase in income, from ₹148,242 in 2020 to ₹205,082 in 2030. Bidar district shows a slight decline in income, from ₹69,115 in 2020 to ₹67,075 in 2030. Kalaburagi district shows a steady increase in income, from ₹90,279 in 2020 to ₹122,269 in 2030. Raichur district shows

a gradual increase in income, from ₹79,893.05 in 2020 to ₹81,640.75 in 2030. Yadgir district shows very slight fluctuations from around ₹68,995.56 in 2020 to ₹68,971.73 in 2030, indicating almost no growth. Kalaburagi exhibits significant income growth, showing positive economic development. Koppal and Raichur both show moderate- and steady-income growth.

Table 4: Forecasting of the Kalyana Karnataka Districts wise per capital Income on Current Prices (in Rs.) and Percentage

Forecasting of the Kalyana Karnataka Districts wise per capital Income on Current Prices (in Rs.) and Percentage												
Year	Ballari	%	Bidar	%	Kalaburagi	%	Koppal	%	Raichur	%	Yadgir	%
2020	148242	4%	69115	0%	90279	3%	80660.39	1%	79893.05	0%	68995.56	0%
2021	153926	4%	68911	0%	93478	3%	81501.92	1%	79946.99	0%	68942.21	0%
2022	159610	3%	68707	0%	96677	3%	82344.54	1%	80250.87	0%	68975.54	0%
2023	165294	3%	68503	0%	99876	3%	83186.43	1%	80388.18	0%	68971.24	0%
2024	170978	3%	68299	0%	103075	3%	84028.51	1%	80567.12	0%	68971.31	0%
2025	176662	14%	68095	-1%	106274	13%	84870.59	5%	80746.06	1%	68971.38	0%
2030	205082		67075	-100%	122269		89080.96		81640.75		68971.73	

Table No. 04 Here's a detailed analysis of the forecasting of the per capita income for the Kalyana Karnataka districts from 2020 to 2030. The Ballari shows consistent growth of 3–4% annually, with a significant jump of 14% in 2025. Bidar shows stagnation in income growth, with minimal decreases over the years. Kalaburagi demonstrates consistent growth at 3% annually, with a significant increase of 13% in 2025, suggesting steady economic development and a potential boost in 2025. The Koppal shows stable but

slow growth of 1% annually, with a more noticeable increase of 5% in 2025. Raichur shows negligible growth around 0% annually, with a slight increase of 1% in 2025. Yadgir shows no significant change in income over the years. Ballari and Kalaburagi: Both districts show significant and consistent growth, with a notable spike in 2025. Bidar exhibits a stagnation or slight decline in income, and Raichur and Yadgir both display minimal to no growth.

Table 5: ANOVA of The Kalyana Karnataka Districts Wise Per Capital Income At Current Prices (In Rs.)

ANOVA Results						
Source of Variation	SS	DF	MS	F	p-value	F-Crit
Between Groups	13593294309	5	2718658862	13.62822029	1.74108E-07	2.477168673
Within Groups	7181548061	36	199487446.1			
Total	20774842370	41				

Table No: 05 shows the result of one-way ANOVA. The results of the Null Hypothesis rejected because the p-value is less than 0.05 at a significant level of 5%. Hence

alternative hypothesis that is “there is a significant deviation in per capital income among Kalyana Karnataka districts”.

Table 6: Correlation of Kalyana Karnataka Districts wise per capital at Current Prices (in Rs.)

Correlation of Kalyana Karnataka Districts wise per capital at Current Prices (in Rs.)						
	Ballari	Bidar	Kalaburagi	Koppal	Raichur	Yadgir
Ballari	1					
Bidar	0.983976117	1				
Kalaburagi	0.965609256	0.966372601	1			
Koppal	0.970167042	0.977080975	0.98133313	1		
Raichur	0.989920871	0.971077159	0.97468537	0.9627447	1	
Yadgir	0.943923445	0.9679363	0.91620552	0.9384317	0.900295228	1

Table No. 06 The provided table displays the correlation coefficients between the per capita incomes of different districts in Kalyana, Karnataka. Ballari and Raichur (0.989920871). indicate very similar economic patterns.

Raichur and Yadgir (0.900295228). Though there is still a strong positive correlation, all districts have a high degree of positive correlation because all correlation results are approximately greater than 0.90.

Table 7: Per-capita GDDP of Karnataka’s districts in FY 20

Sl. No.	Poorest Districts		Middle Districts		Richest Districts	
	District	Per-capita GDDP	District	Per-capita GDDP	District	Per-capita GDDP
1	Kalaburagi	1,16,088	Ballari	1,97,022	No Districts	
2	Koppal	1,26,766				
3	Bidar	1,27,306				
4	Yadgir	1,29,006				
5	Raichur	1,33,197				

Sources: Karnataka Economic Survey 2021-22

Table No. 07 The table presents a classification of districts in the Kalyana Karnataka region based on their per capita Gross District Domestic Product (GDDP). The districts are categorized into three groups: poorest, middle, and richest, based on their per capita GDDP. Kalaburagi has the lowest per capita GDDP of ₹1,16,088 among the listed districts, indicating it is the least economically developed district in the region. The per capita GDDP increases slightly for each

subsequent district, with Raichur having the highest per capita GDDP among the poorest districts at ₹1,33,197. Ballari stands out with a significantly higher per capita GDDP of ₹1,97,022 compared to the poorest districts. The absence of any district in the "Richest Districts" category suggests that there are no districts in the Kalyana Karnataka region with exceptionally high per capita GDDP.

Table 8: Per-capita GDDP of Karnataka’s districts in FY 2030 (estimated data)

Sl. No.	Karnataka	District	Per-capita income FY-2020	Predictable in 2030
1	Developing district	Ballari	1,97,022	205082
2	Less-Developed district	Kalburgi,	1,16,088	122269
		Raichur,	1,33,197	81640.75
		Koppal.	1,26,766	89080.96
3	Least-Developed district	Bidar,	1,27,306	67075
		Yadgir	1,29,006	68971.73

Sources: Karnataka Economic Survey 2021-22 and forecasting data.

Table No. 10 The table categorizes districts in Karnataka based on their per capita income in FY-2020 and provides predicted per capita incomes for 2030. Ballari is categorized as a developing district with a relatively high per capita income (1,97,022) in 2020. The predicted income for 2030 shows continued growth in 2050–2022. Less-Developed Districts Kalburgi district per-capita income FY-2020: ₹1,16,088 and predictable in 2030: ₹1,22,269. Raichur district per-capita income FY-2020: ₹1,33,197. Predictable in 2030: ₹81,640.75 and Koppal district per-capita income FY-2020: ₹1,26,766 and predictable in 2030: ₹89,080.96.

along with Road, water, education, health, and development projects, Special Accelerated irrigation construction Development Project, and increasing connectivity in Income backward areas. now removing imbalances.

The government should guarantee the accessibility of such necessities as clean water, basic health facilities, and free education, including shelter while also providing them, which would minimize the economic disparity in backward regions.

8. Policy implication/remedial measures of the inter-district disparities in the Kalyana Karnataka region.

- **Special Area Development Programmes:** The process of undertaking schemes has been to improve hilly areas and tribal regions, particularly places that are prone to drought, and be implemented in the backward regions.
- **Development Programmes:** It develops programs for irrigation and power, communication, and transportation in drought-prone areas, as well as regional development initiatives, and agriculture. and improving facilities and services to people's standard of living increase in backward regions.
- **Diffusion of industrial infrastructure activity:** In the location of public sector projects, the claims of relatively and infrastructure implement speciality programs increased in backward areas have been. Also,

9. Conclusion and Recommendations

The main purpose of the current study is to examine the inter-district income disparities in the Kalyana Karnataka Region per capital income as well as the causes and remedial measures of Income disparities. Due to the prevalence of underdeveloped and backward regions, and Government of Karnataka released special grants and implemented programs in the Kalyana Karnataka Region. However, it has been noted that there are differences between inter-income disparities at the district level in the Kalyana Karnataka Region. Finally, the income disparity between regions in the Kalyana Karnataka districts was determined. In the Kalyana Karnataka Region, there is a need for employment creation that can raise living standards and for the adoption of long-term policies. To boost overall progress in the Kalyana Karnataka Region, the government

must act. Therefore, the government should plan and invest in least-developed districts in a responsible manner. Finally, recommend that more research be done to determine the reasons behind economic inequality in this region.

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